

Empowering Community Participation in Funding Education at MA Queen Al Khotijah Cilacap

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe the empowerment of community participation in financing education at MA Queen Al Khotijah Cilacap. This research is a descriptive research with a qualitative approach. The informants of this research are school principals and school treasurers. Data collection methods used in the form of interviews, observation, and documentation. The data validity test was carried out by triangulation of techniques and sources. Data were analyzed qualitatively with Miles and Huberman's interactive model. The results of the study show that: The determination of education funding at MA Queen Al Khotijah gathers the guardians of the students to sit together and have deliberations. In this deliberation, the Supreme Court explained plans for MA funding needs, especially for the payment of teachers' and assistants' salaries. Then, the administrators and the student's guardian agree and make a joint decision on the nominal amount that must be paid by the student's guardian each month. Not only that, as a form of report and evaluation, the administrators also report to the student's guardian regarding monthly income and expenses during the student guardian meeting, especially those related to paying the salaries of teachers and assistants. In addition, there are also several donors who provide funding for MA apart from BOS funds

INTRODUCTION

Education funding is not only the responsibility of the government, but also the responsibility of regional (provincial and district/city) governments. This is as regulated in several articles in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System including Article 11 Paragraph 2 which states that the Government and Regional Governments are obliged to guarantee the availability of funds to provide education for every citizen aged seven to fifteen year. Then in article 12 paragraph 1 It is stated that every student in each educational unit is entitled to a scholarship for outstanding achievers whose parents cannot afford to pay for their education and get tuition fees for those whose parents cannot afford to pay for their education. In addition, it is also stated in Article 12 Paragraph 2 that every student is obliged to share in the costs of providing education, except for students who are exempt from this obligation in accordance with applicable laws and regulations. Article 49 Paragraph 1 states that education funds other than teacher salaries and official education costs are allocated a minimum of 20% of the State Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBN) for the education sector and a minimum of 20% of the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD). The existence of the education budget is expected to improve the quality of education in Indonesian.

Education is a learning process that has a view to realizing a systematic learning orientation in order to develop individual skills, mature student morals, and prepare individuals who are beneficial to their environment. According to Kristin, education is seen as a right aimed at society and something of value in one's life. Education as a complex process with the aim of developing, conditioning, and creating humans as complete (perfect) beings. Within the scope of education, teachers play a very strategic role in achieving educational orientation. The success or failure of an implementation of learning is very dependent on the teacher. Teachers have a very difficult task, namely they are required to find innovative learning strategies that can make children enthusiastic about participating in learning. The success of the teaching and learning process can be measured through students' ability to reflect and understand the material well.

Education has an important role to educate the nation's generation and develop the whole person. Education can be influenced by various factors that exist in life. Through this paradigm, education is expected to provide solutions to fight challenges and problems that will occur in life. The implementation of Law Number 22 of 1999 concerning Regional Autonomy and Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government includes consequences for wider autonomy and decentralization of areas of regional authority, including education. Specifically in the field of education, the Decree of the Minister of National Education Number 044/U/2002 concerning School Committees and Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, explicitly affirms regional authority to manage the education sector.

In the perspective and practice of regional autonomy, education is one area whose management is fully decentralized to the regions (districts/cities).

This momentum simultaneously and immanently the regions must empower themselves and adapt to the new paradigm of education management which emphasizes active and open participation of the community starting from planning, organizing, implementing and controlling educational processes and outcomes.

Schools as educational units that are at the forefront of the implementation of education are placed as an institution in the midst of society that has its own characteristics, planning, decision-making and management units. This paradigm is not only an answer to demands for autonomy and education reform down to the unit (school) level, which is expected to be able to encourage school empowerment to adapt to the levels of change, demands and values that develop in their sociological environment. It also means that schools must pay attention to and utilize aspects of community participation in the implementation of education which has strategic roles and functions. According to Pidarta, the expected school empowerment perspective is analogously described: Schools are not justified as water towers, that is, they merge into one with the community without giving any identity. He is also not justified as an ivory tower that isolates itself from the surrounding community. A true educational institution is like a light tower, which is in the community and at the same time provides information to the local community. Educational institutions must remain rooted in the local community, pay attention to the ideas of the local community, carry out their aspirations, make use of local facilities for learning, and adapt to the living habits of the local community. Meanwhile he is trying to improve the way of life and people's lives by providing information, creating superior seeds, creating new technologies.

In this perspective the school functions as the heart of society which must be designed to be able to contribute to efforts to improve the quality of life of the nation. Optimizing resources related to school empowerment is the most appropriate alternative to realize the school's function. Empowerment is also intended to provide broader autonomy in solving problems faced by schools. Empowerment of these schools has far-reaching interests in the future. This is based on the increasingly complex reality of social life in society. The higher the level and social life, the higher the desired demands, which in the end these demands lead to education.

The community believes that education/schools are capable of answering and anticipating the various challenges they face. Community participation in the field of education has a very important and strategic position. This is officially recognized, both in laws and in several ministerial regulations. According to the Law on the National Education System Number 20 of 2003, education is a shared responsibility between families, communities and the government. In a broader scope, society is also responsible for education, at the macro level, the government is responsible for education for its citizens. Decree of the Minister of National Education Number 044/U/2002 which became the basis for the formation of school committees and education boards, the purpose of forming committees is to accommodate, channel

community aspirations and initiatives in producing operational policies and educational programs in education units, increase the responsibility and active participation of all levels of society in the administration of education in education units, and creating a transparent, accountable and democratic atmosphere and condition in the implementation and quality education services in education units .

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

A qualitative descriptive approach is prioritized by finding existing indicators. In finding existing information and indicators, data collection is more on data collection methods in the form of interviews, documentation, with analysis focused on listening, seeing, interacting, asking, talking, exploring, recording important notes on matters related to empowering community participation in financing education at MA Queen Al Khotijah Cilacap. In this study, the data collection method was carried out directly to the field using observation, interview and documentation techniques. The data analysis phase uses interactive analysis by presenting the results of the research conducted. The steps in this analysis are: a) data reduction, b) data presentation, c) drawing conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Public participation is also an important part in the implementation of financing management. For this reason, efforts to mobilize community participation for the implementation of education need to be made, in addition to the implementation of other aspects in the implementation of financial management. The community is the first and foremost environment for the school, all students in the school come from the surrounding community, the community will live around the school 24 hours a day. The community is one of the sources of income for the government's money, therefore the community is an important asset in development, including in education financing. In accordance with what was conveyed by Sulistyorini, realizing quality education requires comprehensive and professional management of existing resources in an educational institution. and one of the resources that needs to be managed properly in order to create quality education is the problem of finance or education funding.

In this context, Sulistyorini emphasized that finance or financing is a source of funds needed by every educational institution as a tool to complete various learning facilities and infrastructure, improve teacher welfare, services, implementation of supervision programs, and operational needs of other educational institutions. So it is not an exaggeration to say that education financing is vital for an educational institution at MA Queen Al Khotijah Cilacap in realizing quality education, because quality educational activities

certainly require adequate handling in terms of finance where this is closely related to financial resources. strong educational funding or funding as well. Sources of education funding are all parties that provide subsidized assistance and donations received by school institutions, either from official sources or from the community itself on a regular basis. The definition of sources of education funding indicates that the success and quality of education supported by strong education funding is not only the responsibility of the school or educational institution, but also the responsibility of the environment, namely the family (guardians of students) and the community. Therefore, education is a shared responsibility between the government, families (guardians of students), and society. This also confirms that parents or guardians of students and the community have an obligation to participate and share the needs in the implementation of education, especially in terms of education funding.

Siti Irene Astuti Dwiningrum confirmed that parental involvement in funding or funding education makes a significant contribution to improving the quality of schools or educational institutions. School autonomy in financing is able to provide strength for schools to attract funds from outside because schools are considered to have the ability to self-fund for the development of superior programs so that even outsiders or the government give confidence to schools. From what was conveyed by Siti Irene Astuti Dwiningrum, when examined further it can be understood that the involvement of parents or guardians of students in financing education makes a positive contribution to educational institutions to meet the completeness and needs of its implementation. The greater the funds spent by parents or guardians at least indicates the greater their participation in encouraging the improvement of the quality of educational institutions.

When the researcher conducted an interview with the Head of MA Queen Al Khotijah Cilacap, the researcher found information that the community has a very important role in the financing management process. From this interview, H. Irsyadul Umam, M. Hum. said that in the financing process for the sustainability of public education has a very important and active role.

As for community participation in financing the education of MA Queen Al Khotijah, H. Irsyadul Umam, M. Hum.. explained that the funding at MA Queen Al Khotijah cannot be separated from the amount of support and participation from the community. H. Irsyadul Umam, M.Hum. mentioned that most or almost all sources of funding for MA Queen Al Khotijah education come from the community, especially the guardians of students and administrators and they are also involved in planning and decision making in

various activities especially in terms of financing. H. Irsyadul Umam, M. Hum. gave an example that to determine the nominal or amount of students' tuition fees, the management at MA Queen Al Khotijah gathered the guardians of the students to sit together and have a deliberation. In this deliberation, the Supreme Court explained plans for MA funding needs, especially for the payment of teachers' and assistants' salaries. Then, the administrators and the student's guardian agree and make a joint decision on the nominal amount that must be paid by the student's guardian each month. Not only that, as a form of report and evaluation, administrators also report to student guardians regarding monthly income and expenditure during student guardian meetings, especially those related to payment of teacher and companion salaries. In addition, there are also several donors who provide funding for MA apart from BOS funds.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research and discussion regarding educational financing at MA Queen Al Khotijah, the following conclusions can be drawn: Determining the financing of education at MA Queen Al Khotijah gathers the guardians of the students to sit together and have deliberations. In this deliberation, the Supreme Court explained plans for MA funding needs, especially for the payment of teachers' and assistants' salaries. Then, the administrators and the student's guardian agree and make a joint decision on the nominal amount that must be paid by the student's guardian each month. Not only that, as a form of report and evaluation, administrators also report to student guardians regarding monthly income and expenditure during student guardian meetings, especially those related to payment of teacher and companion salaries. In addition, there are also several donors who provide funding for MA apart from BOS funds.

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